

**ANALYSIS OF SUPPRESSION OF FREE-EDGE DELAMINATION
BY INTRODUCING ADHESIVE LAYER**

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the present study is to demonstrate qualitatively, a procedure of suppressing delamination mode of failure in composite laminates. A number of delamination prone laminates are considered. These laminates with and without adhesive layer at appropriate interfaces are analyzed and tested for inplane unidirectional loading conditions. It has been demonstrated that the delamination can be suppressed by using adhesive layer at interfaces of high interlaminar stresses. This procedure has led to significantly higher ultimate strength of laminates with adhesive layers as compared to those without adhesive layer.

INTRODUCTION

Delamination is one of the most feared of modes of failure in composite laminates. Extensive work has been done in the analysis of free-edge effects in layered composites [1-5]. In the last few years authors conducted many studies [6-8], to investigate the onset of delamination and demonstrated with conclusive evidence, both experimentally and theoretically, the onset of delamination stimulated either by the interlaminar normal stress component σ_z or by the interlaminar shear stress component τ_{xz} . Following this understanding, studies were carried

out toward developing schemes to suppress delamination by hybridization [9]. Other authors have done some work [10-12] on the title topic by using approximate methods of predicting interlaminar stresses, but not in a detail and precision as that of the present study.

In the present work, both theoretical and experimental studies are done to investigate the onset of delamination in different laminates with the purpose of suppressing delamination by introducing adhesive layer. A number of composite laminates prone to delamination due to the interlaminar stress component σ_z are considered. On the basis of the stress analysis of these laminates, the onset of delamination load and interface were predicted [7]. Laminates with the adhesive layers at the interface of high stress levels responsible for the onset of delamination in pure graphite epoxy, are prepared, tested and analyzed. The laminates were co-cured with the adhesive layer stacked at appropriate interfaces. The T300/1034C graphite epoxy material and the interleaved film CYCOM HST-7 adhesive manufactured by American Cyanamid was chosen for this investigation.

Stress analysis for the present work is done by the use of global-local variational model [3]. Figures showing the stress distribution at midsurface and other interfaces of different laminates are given. The inspection of these stress distributions for without-the-adhesive layer laminates indicates that under tensile loading, the delamination should occur at the midsurface. Experimental investigations have shown that the failure occurs at the predicted interface. To avoid delamination at the midsurface of the laminate, adhesive layers at appropriate interfaces are introduced and tested.

The further inspection of the stress distribution shows that there is a significant difference in the stress component at the midsurface and the adjoining interface (90/-45), between the results for laminates with and without adhesive layer. To avoid delamination in laminates with adhesive layer at the mid surface, adhesive layers at the interfaces next to mid surface were introduced. These laminates when tested have shown delamination resistance at those interfaces.

PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

Figure 1 shows the laminate geometry, coordinate axis, and the direction of applied stress. The magnitude of the induced interlaminar and inplane stress components is dependent upon the stacking sequence and applied load. Any one of these stress components or a combination there of may be responsible for failure of the laminate.

LAMINATE GEOMETRY

FIG. 1—Boundary-value problem.

The distribution of interlaminar stress components σ_z , τ_{xz} and τ_{yz} for a number of laminates made of T300/1034-C graphite epoxy material have been determined by the Extended Reissner's Variational Principle [1,3]. The following material properties were used for the stress analysis

$$E_{11} = 137.9 \text{ GPa (20 Msi)}$$

$$E_{22} = E_{33} = 9.653 \text{ GPa (1.4 Msi)}$$

$$G_{12} = G_{13} = 5.516 \text{ GPa (0.8 Msi)}$$

$$G_{32} = 4.137 \text{ GPa (0.6 Msi)}$$

$$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.3, \quad \nu_{23} = 0.54$$

where E , G , ν , and Subscripts 1,2, and 3 have their usual meaning.

The material properties of the adhesive material CYCOM HST-7 by American Cyanamid are given below:

$$E=3.7 \text{ GPa (.54 Msi)}, \quad \nu=0.3$$

ONSET OF DELAMINATION PREDICTION AND EXPERIMENTS

On the basis of earlier experience of delamination prone laminates, the following laminates are investigated:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} (0/\pm 45/90)_S & (0/\pm 45/90/\bar{F})_S & (0/\pm 45/F/90/\bar{F})_S \\ (\pm 30_2/90_2)_S & (\pm 30_2/90_2/\bar{F})_S & (\pm 30_2/F/90_2/\bar{F})_S \end{array}$$

In these laminates F denotes an adhesive layer of thickness one fifth of that of the T300/1034C layer thickness, \bar{F} denotes the half adhesive layer. Figure 2 shows the stress distribution in $(0/\pm 45/90)_S$ and figure 5 that for $(\pm 30_2/90_2)_S$ laminate with and without adhesive layer located at their mid surfaces. The interface at which the stress distribution is given in these figures is marked by an arrowhead. In both the cases of laminates analyzed, σ_z is predominant at the mid surface.

In stress analysis of figures 2 and 5 the horizontal axis represents the location along the width of the laminate. The results are plotted for points along the width, at the appropriate interface, up to a distance equal to the half laminate thickness including the free edge.

For the prediction of the interface at which the onset of delamination occurs, we inspect the stress levels at the interfaces. The interface having the lowest relevant directional strength to stress component (in this case, average stress component) ratio should develop damage. In certain cases, it has been observed that the interaction of stress components play a significant role in influencing the onset of delamination load. In this study we are not considering the interaction of stresses. However, in the case of the laminates under investigation, the stress distribution given in figures 2 and 5 prompt that the onset of delamination in pure graphite epoxy laminates (without adhesive layer), should occur at the mid surface due to σ_z . In the same figures, the stress levels for laminates with adhesive layer are presented. It can be seen that the stress component σ_z , for these laminates, at the

mid plane is considerably lower than that for laminate without the adhesive layer. Besides, during curing the presence of the adhesive layer may influence the strength characteristics of the adjacent T300/1034-C layers. This aspect can not be included in the analysis under the present state of the investigations.

Table 1 shows the facts and figures of the mechanical testing for all the laminates. The effective Young's modulus, Poisson ratio, onset of delamination stress and strain (where applicable), first ply failure and ultimate strengths are given for each laminate. In each of these laminates the given results are the averages of values for two samples.

TABLE 1

	E_{11} , MSI (GPa) *	ν_{21}	σ_D , KSI (MPa)	ϵ_D %	σ_u , KSI (MPa)	FPF, KSI (MPa)
$(0/\pm 45/90)_S$	8.52 (59)	0.30	66.20 (456)	0.795	80.786 (557)	40.79 (281)
$(0/\pm 45/90/\bar{F})_S$	7.61 (52)	0.30	76.83 (524)	1.01	84.87 (585)	46.15 (318)
$(0/\pm 45/F/90/\bar{F})_S$	7.48 (52)	0.31	--	--	92.76 (640)	42.11 (290)
$(\pm 30_2/90_2)_S$	7.30 (50)	0.31	32.361 (223)	0.450	32.911 (227)	24.993 (172)
$(\pm 30_2/90_2/\bar{F})_S$	7.91 (55)	0.30	34.14 (235)	0.446	35.56 (245)	30.32 (209)
$(\pm 30_2/F/90_2/\bar{F})_S$	7.09 (49)	0.30	---	---	42.44 (293)	30.40 (210)

* Values within parenthesis are in metric units.

Figure 3 shows the stress strain plots for $(0/\pm 45/90)_S$ and $(0/\pm 45/90/\bar{F})_S$ laminates. Figure 4 depicts the microphotographs of abovementioned tested laminates. The stress strain plots are given for two or three repeated unidirectional loading cases. In the first loading the sample is loaded up to a load corresponding to a solid circle and unloaded. Then it is reloaded till ultimate failure (second time or third time)

Figure 2: Stress analysis of $(0/\pm 45/90)_S$ and $(0/\pm 45/90)_F$ laminates.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3: Stress-strain plots for $(0/\pm 45/90)_s$, $(0/\pm 45/90/\bar{F})_s$ and $(0/\pm 45/F/90/\bar{F})_s$ Laminates.

(a) Microphotograph for $(0/\pm 45/90)_S$ laminate
 $\sigma_D = 456 \text{ MPa (66.2 KSI)}$.

(b) Microphotograph for $(0/\pm 45/90/\bar{F})_S$ laminate
 $\sigma_D = 524 \text{ MPa (76.83 KSI)}$.

Figure 4: Microphotographs of delaminated $(0/\pm 45/90)_S$ and $(0/\pm 45/90/\bar{F})_S$ laminates.

represented by symbol at the extreme top of the curve. These stress strain plots show the difference in failure modes in three different cases of this laminate. In the case of a pure $(0/\pm 45/90)_S$, figures 2 and 4(a), laminate transverse cracking occurred at 281 MPa (40.79 KSI) and delamination occurred at the mid plane due to σ_z at an applied load of 457 MPa (66.2 KSI). The ultimate strength was 557 MPa (80.79 KSI).

In the case of a $(0/\pm 45/90/\bar{F})_S$ laminate, figures 2 and 4(b), the transverse cracking initiated at 318 MPa (46.15 KSI), the delamination took place at an applied stress of 524 MPa (76.83 KSI) at 45/-45 and/or -45/90 interfaces and the ultimate strength was 585 MPa (84.87 KSI). The location of delamination interface has changed as a result of introduction of an adhesive layer at the mid surface.

In the case of a $(0/\pm 45/F/90/\bar{F})_S$ laminate the first ply failure took place at 290 MPa (42.11 KSI), where as the ultimate strength was 667 MPa (92.76 KSI). The delamination took place at the mid surface at a load of 594 MPa (86.11 KSI) which is near ultimate strength 667 MPa (92.76 KSI) of this laminate. This is about 1.4 times the load at which delamination took place in a laminate without an adhesive layer. Thus the introduction of an additional layer at -45/90 interface has helped avoid delamination of that interface.

Similar observations are made in the case of $(\pm 30_2/90_2)_S$ laminate, figure 5. Without adhesive layer, it has been shown that the laminate delaminates at the mid surface due to σ_z , at an applied in-plane stress of about 223 MPa (32.36 KSI). In the case of a laminate with an adhesive layer at the mid plane, it has been seen that the delamination does occur, but that is apparently initiated by the transverse crack in 90° layers and the adhesive layer. The delamination occurred at 234 MPa (34.14 KSI), which is the ultimate strength of the laminate. On the introduction of an adhesive layer at an interface -30/90, it has been observed that the delamination is completely suppressed for up to a load of 293 MPa (42.472 KSI), which is the ultimate strength of the laminate.

Microphotograph of delaminated $(\pm 30_2/90_2/\bar{F})_S$ laminate.

$\sigma_D = 235 \text{ MPa (34.14 KSI)}$.

Figure 5: Stress analysis and microphotographs of delaminated $(\pm 30_2/90_2)_S$ and $(\pm 30_2/90_2/\bar{F})_S$ laminates.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Two sets of laminates, prone to delamination have been studied. In pure laminates, the delamination takes place at the mid surface. The introduction of an adhesive layer at the mid surface suppressed the delamination at that surface and enhanced the ultimate strength of these laminates. The further introduction of adhesive layers at interfaces next to the mid surface has helped avoiding delamination. The stress analysis has shown that the introduction of adhesive layers at different interfaces has helped reduce stress concentration. If we look at it with an average stress at the free edge point of view, the stress concentration factor reduction is not very significant. Thus it is anticipated that the high strength of the adhesive layer in comparison to that of 90° layer has helped avoid the delamination. Since, we anticipate delamination at the interface, the co-curing of adhesive layer might have transmitted its strength characteristics to the adjacent layers, at the interfaces. No account of these factors is made in the present analysis.

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